

MECHANISM OF MUTAROTATION OF D-OXYMETHYLENE CAMPHOR.

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Mutarotation of *d*-oxymethylenecamphor has been examined with reference to its fractional change in rotation (when it becomes constant) being independent of initial concentration. Results on the velocity of mutarotation from copper salt indicate that the mutarotation consists in the transformation of enol into keto form.

Pope and Read (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 94, 176) and Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*Annalen*, 1894, 281, 331) have observed that *d*-oxymethylenecamphor shows a change in optical rotation with respect to time, both in benzene and alcohol. The results in alcohol refer to one concentration only, while in benzene they have studied the change for three concentrations.

Pope and Read (*loc. cit.*) have not shown that fractional change in rotation, when it has become constant, is independent of initial concentration, a condition necessary for mutarotation. We have, therefore, examined the question and our results in absolute ethyl alcohol are given below.

TABLE I.

Wt. of the substance.	Length of the tube.	Time.	α_D .	α_∞/α_0 .
2.454 (g. /100 c.c.)	1 d. cm.	0 hr.	4.85	0.928
"	"	26	4.50	
2.518	"	0	5.00	0.930
"	"	26	4.65	
1.878	"	0	3.70	0.932
"	"	20	3.45	
5.767	"	0	11.2	0.941
"	"	48	10.55	
1.280	"	0	2.50	0.920
"	"	24	2.30	
6.183	"	0	12.0	0.933
"	"	48	11.2	
2.8616	2 d. cm.	0	10.45	0.938
"	"	24	9.80	
1.6584	"	0	6.4	0.937
"	"	24	6.0	

The above results, therefore, indicate that *d*-oxymethylenecamphor shows mutarotation.

Although Pope and Read (*loc. cit.*) have observed the optical rotation of *d*-oxymethylenecamphor to change with time, no attempt so far has been made to study the rate of this change. Our results in ethyl alcohol with and without HCl as catalyst are recorded below.

In determining the order of the reaction, the difference between the constant reading (a_{∞}) and reading at any time t , is taken to be proportional to the concentration of *d*-oxymethylenecamphor at that time and is therefore $= a - x$, where 'a' is the initial concentration when $t = 0$.

TABLE II.

Wt. of the substance = 5.757 g. in 100 c.c. a_{∞} is in 1 d.cm. tube.
Temp = 24.5°.

			$K_1 =$				$K_1 =$
t .	a_{∞} .	$a - x$.	$\frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.	t .	a_{∞} .	$a - x$.	$\frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.
0 min.	11.2	0.65 (a)		135 min.	10.80	0.25	0.00706
30	11.1	0.55	0.00557	210	10.70	0.15	0.00697
55	11.0	0.45	0.00667	275	10.65	0.10	0.00686
80	10.90	0.35	0.00773	∞	10.55	...	
100	10.85	0.30	0.00771				

TABLE III.

Wt. of the substance = 6.183 g. in 100 c.c. a_{∞} is in 1 d.cm. tube.
Temp. = 25.5°.

			$K_1 =$				$K_1 =$
t .	a_{∞} .	$a - x$.	$\frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.	t .	a_{∞} .	$a - x$.	$\frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.
0 min.	12.0	0.80 (a)		91 min.	11.60	0.40	0.00759
15	11.90	0.70	0.00888	108	11.55	0.35	0.00764
35	11.80	0.60	0.00821	134	11.50	0.30	0.00731
50	11.75	0.55	0.00745	155	11.45	0.25	0.00750
60	11.70	0.50	0.00782	195	11.40	0.20	0.00708
76	11.65	0.45	0.00757	450	11.25	0.05	0.00614
				∞	11.20

TABLE IV.

Wt. of the substance = 3.6500 g. in 100 c.c. 0.2 C.c. of 2.117*N*-HCl were added. Temp. = 24°. a_0 is in 2 d.cm. tube.

t .	a_0 .	$a-x$.	$K_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.
0 min.	13.25	1.40 (a)	...
35	12.80	0.95	0.0110
190	12.05	0.20	0.0101
225	12.00	0.15	0.0099
260	11.85

TABLE V.

Wt. of the substance = 2.1896 g. in 100 c.c. 0.2 C.c. of 2.117*N*-HCl added. Temp. = 20.7°. a_0 is in 2 d.cm. tube.

t .	a_0 .	$a-x$.	$K_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.	t .	a_0 .	$a-x$.	$K_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.
0 min.	8.30	1.40 (a)	...	162 min.	7.60	0.70	0.00414
18	8.20	1.30	0.00414	190	7.50	0.60	0.00437
37	8.05	1.15	0.00529	232	7.40	0.50	0.00437
49	8.00	1.10	0.00483	254	7.35	0.45	0.00437
63	7.95	1.05	0.00460	284	7.30	0.40	0.00437
78	7.90	1.00	0.00437	438	7.05	0.15	0.00506
92	7.80	0.90	0.00483	476	7.05	0.15	0.00460
108	7.75	0.85	0.00460	501	6.95	0.05	0.00667
127	7.70	0.80	0.00437	∞	6.90

Estimation of the enolic Form.

Attempts were made by us to see whether ordinary *d*-oxymethylene-camphor exists mainly in its keto or enol form. Enol form of the compound, as it contains OH group in the side-chain, should behave as an acid, and hence could be titrated with sodium hydroxide. The amount of alkali required is therefore a direct measure of the amount of enolic form in the given amount of the compound, provided no change occurs during titration.

The other method that was employed for this keto-enol estimation is due to Heiber (*Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 902). We modified the method as follows.

Instead of adding copper acetate solution in alcohol-chloroform mixture, aqueous copper acetate was added to the substance dissolved in alcohol. The precipitate of copper salt formed was then extracted with chloroform and the chloroformic solution was then decomposed by dilute sulphuric acid. The copper thus liberated was then estimated volumetrically.

TABLE VI.

Estimation of enol form by NaOH titration

<i>d</i> -Oxymethylenecamphor.		Enol %.	Vol. of NaOH. (0.0303N)
Wt. taken	Wt. calc.		
0.1913g.	0.1848g.	96.6	33.90 c.c.
0.17c4	0.1668	94.4	29.50
0.1600	0.1567	97.9	28.75
0.1830	0.1820	99.4	33.40

It seems therefore that *d*-oxymethylenecamphor exists mainly as an enol, although it is not unlikely that addition of alkali might be converting the keto form into enol form.

TABLE VII.

Estimation of enol by forming copper salt, (Heiber's method).
0.02658N-thiosulphate used for titration.

Wt. of substance.	Vol. required (Cu salt).	Wt. of substance calc.	Enol %.
0.0918g.	8.3 c.c.	0.07941g.	86.5
0.1458	12.3	0.11770	80.7
0.2083	18.0	0.17220	82.6
0.6033	—	0.49560	82.5
0.1180	—	0.09710	82.3
0.3170	—	0.26020	82.0
0.2362	—	0.19410	82.2
0.0568	—	0.04670	82.0

These results confirm that *d*-oxymethylenecamphor mainly exists in enolic form, the percentage of enol being about 80.

Velocity of Mutarotation of d-Oxymethylenecamphor.

A known weight of the substance was dissolved in a known volume of absolute alcohol. A known concentration of catalyst (HCl) was added and the amount of enol was estimated in terms of thiosulphate required for a definite volume of solution taken out from time to time. The results are as follows.

TABLE VIII.

1.4123 G. of substance dissolved in 50 c. c. of absolute alcohol. 0.2 c. c. 2.117N-HCl added, 5 c. c. of the solution titrated at a time against 0.2776N-thiosulphate solution. Temp. = 23.8°.

<i>t.</i>	Thio required.	Enol %.	$K_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$
0 min.	13.5 c. c.	95.5%	
65	11.2	85.6	0.00159
120	11.7	82.7	0.00120
180	11.4	81.3	0.00094
24 hours	11.1	78.5	0.000133

It is clear from above that the reaction is not unimolecular.

TABLE IX.

0.8382 G. of the substance dissolved in 50 c. c. of alcohol. Temp. 43.8°. Conc. of HCl same as above.

<i>t.</i>	Thio required.	Enol %.	$K_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$
0 min	12 c. c.	85.8	
30	6.0	71.5	0.00607
60	5.0	59.6	0.00607
90	4.25	50.6	0.00589
120	3.85	45.9	0.00520
150	3.30	39.3	0.00518
180	3.15	37.5	0.00455
21 hour:	2.40	29.2	

The velocity coefficients slowly fall with increase of time.

DISCUSSION.

The results of keto-enol estimation by Heiber method (*loc. cit.*) and by titration with alkali clearly establish the fact that *d*-oxymethylenecamphor mainly exists in the enolic form. This view confirms the observation of Brühl (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, **34**, 1), Federlin (*Annalen*, 1907, **386**, 251) and of Pope and Read (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **94**, 176) made by refractometric, calorimetric and polarimetric methods respectively. Brühl (*loc. cit.*) and Federlin (*loc. cit.*) suggested that the constitution of *d*-oxymethylenecamphor is represented as

Pope and Read (*loc. cit.*) have criticised the work on the ground that these workers have not considered the possibility of the formation of equilibrium mixture of two enolic modifications suggested by Claisen (*Annalen*, 1894, **281**, 306).

Type (I)

They have come to the conclusion that *d*-oxymethylenecamphor shows mutarotation due to this change of one enolic form into another. Our results with velocity of mutarotation as investigated by copper salt method clearly point out that the amount of enol decreases with time; and since it is the only the enol which can form copper salt, this decrease clearly indicates that muta change consists in the transformation of enol into keto form.

Type (II)

Pope and Read (*loc. cit.*) have offered no experimental support to their suggestion except the work of Brühl (*loc. cit.*) and Federlin (*loc. cit.*) which in reality does not exclude the possibility of keto change during mutarotation. Moreover, Pope and Read did not show that the ratio of final rotation to initial rotation is constant whatever may be the initial concentration of the substance. However, our polarimetric results

show that ratio of the final rotation to initial rotation is constant and is independent of initial concentration. But this constancy need not necessarily confirm the view of Pope and Read for, even in case of equilibrium of the type (II), similar results are possible. Study of mutarotation by polarimeter is therefore not enough to draw any conclusion since both constitutions are admissible. The investigation by copper salt method for enolic form therefore is the only way to decide between the two possibilities. The fact that the amount of enol decreases with time clearly confirms our suggestion that in mutarotation, enol changes to the keto form. If both forms are enolic the weight of copper salt formed with time should have remained constant.

There is no doubt therefore that mutarotation involves a change from enol to keto form (Type II). This change may be either an equilibrium change or one-sided.

The constancy of the ratio of initial rotation to final rotation cannot decide between these possibilities, since whether the change is complete or fractional, in this case change being from one molecule to one molecule the ratio must come out to be a constant. Results with copper salt method, however, support the equilibrium view. For if the reaction is one-sided all enol will become keto at the end and no copper salt will be formed. This, however, is not observed. When the concentration of the enol form has fallen to a certain extent there is no further change.

The change associated with mutarotation cannot be of such a simple type. In that case the calculation of velocity constants by the formulae

$$K_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$$

should not give constant results. Actually polarimetric results give a constant value for velocity coefficient and also for the ratio of final rotation to the initial rotation. However, the monomolecular formula fails when results are expressed in terms of copper salt. It is clear therefore that mutarotation change also involves a side reaction in such a way that the ratio of mutarotation values is not affected.

It seems likely that the mechanism of mutarotational change can be correctly represented as :

At first the enolic form (A) changes into the second enolic form (B) which then forms an equilibrium with (C). It is likely that the form B and

Since initially *d*-oxymethylenecamphor is mainly enolic, there is no B or C. Also when value of copper salt becomes constant with time there is no A and whole is $B + C = a$. The change from $A \rightarrow B$ does not change the weight of copper salt; hence any change in its amount with respect to time must be due the formation of C. Thus we get y or concentration of C at any time. When there is no further fall in the weight of copper salt the weight corresponds to the weight of B at equilibrium. Knowing the corresponding amount of C we get $K = m/y$. a is known, hence $b = a/1 + K$ can be calculated. Thus the above equation and hence the mechanism of mutarotation can be verified. Our results are as follows :

TABLE X.

1.4123 G. of the *d*-oxymethylenecamphor dissolved in 50 c.c. of alcohol. 0.2 c.c. of 2.117*N* HCl added. Temp. = 23.8°. 5 c.c. of the solution were titrated with 0.02776*N* thiosulphate,

t .	Thio.	y_x	K_x	b_x	$b - y_x$	$K_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{b}{b - y}$
0 min.	13.5 c.c.	—	11.1/2.4	—	—	
65	12.2	1.3	= 4.625		1.1	0.0120
120	11.7	1.8	...	$\frac{13.5}{5.625}$	0.6	0.0115
180	11.4	2.1	...	= 2.4	0.3	0.0115
24 hours	11.1	2.4	—	...

TABLE XI.

0.8382 G. of *d*-oxymethylenecamphor dissolved in 50 c.c. of alcohol. 0.2 C.cs. of 2.117*N*-HCl added. Temp. = 33.8°. 25 C.c. of solution were titrated with 0.02776*N*-thiosulphate.

t .	Vol. of thio.	y .	K .	b .	$b - y$.	$K_1 = \frac{x}{t} \log \frac{b}{c-y}$.
0 min	7.2	—	0.5	$\frac{7.2}{1+0.5}$...	
30	6.0	1.2	...	= 4.8	3.6	0.00957
60	5.0	2.2	2.6	0.0103
90	4.25	2.95	1.85	0.0106
120	3.85	3.35	1.45	0.00996
150	3.30	3.90	0.90	0.0110
180	3.15	4.05	0.75	0.0101
21 hours	2.40	4.80

The consistency of the velocity constants clearly confirms the above view about the mechanism of muta-rotational change of *d*-oxymethylene camphor.

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